

A NOVEL COHESIVE MODEL FOR SIMULATING DELAMINATION PROPAGATION IN COMPOSITE LAMINATED STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we have proposed a new cohesive model to stably and accurately simulate delamination propagations in composite laminates under transverse loads. In this model, we set up a pre-softening zone in front of the original softening zone. In this pre-softening zone, the initial stiffness is gradually reduced as the interface strength decreases. However, the onset displacement for starting the real softening process is not changed in this model. The fracture toughness of materials for determining the final displacement of complete decohesion is not changed too. This cohesive model is implemented in the explicit time integration scheme. A DCB problem is employed to analyze the characteristics of the present cohesive model. Moreover, an experimental example of laminates under impact loads is employed to illustrate the validity of the present method.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well known that very complicated damage phenomena occur in composite laminated structures under the transverse loads. Delaminations between multiple laminae are the dominant damages of laminates in this case. Cohesive interface models are widely used to simulate the delamination propagation [1, 2]. However, there are two main problems for the traditional cohesive models. The first one is the numerical instability problem, especially for those interfaces with high strength and high initial stiffness. Some methodologies can be used to remove this numerical instability, e.g., Riks method, as well as the move-limit method [3]. Another problem is the error of peak load in the load-displacement curve when using comparatively coarse meshes. In this paper, we propose a new cohesive model termed as Adaptive Cohesive Model, to stably simulate delamination propagations in composite laminates for comparatively coarse cohesive elements.

2 ADAPTIVE COHESIVE MODEL

As shown in Fig. 1, before the original softening area, we insert a transition area called pre-softening area. In this area, the initial stiffness and interface strength of cohesive element are gradually reduced as shown in Fig. 2 for Mode-I. Assume the current maximum effective displacement at one integration point of cohesive element is δ_m^{\max} , in the pre-softening area, the stiffness and interface strength of at this integration point is linearly updated as follows

$$N_i = \frac{\delta_m^{\max}}{\delta_m^0} (N_{\min} - N_0) + N_0, (N_{\min} < N_0); K_i = \frac{\delta_m^{\max}}{\delta_m^0} (K_{\min} - K_0) + K_0, (K_{\min} < K_0) \quad (1)$$

where N_0 is the initial interface strength, N_{\min} the lower limit of interface strength, K_0 the initial stiffness and K_{\min} is the lower limit of initial stiffness. At the same time, the onset displacement δ_m^0 is not changed. In this case, it can be defined as:

$$\delta_m^0 = \frac{N_0}{K_0} = \frac{N_i(\delta_m^{\max})}{K_i(\delta_m^{\max})} = \frac{N_{\min}}{K_{\min}} \quad (2)$$

Also, to keep the fracture toughness to be constant, i.e., the area of triangles in Figs. 1~2, the final displacement corresponding to the complete decohesion δ_m^{fi} is adjusted as shown in Figs. 1~2. Once entering into the softening process, i.e. $\delta_m^{\max} > \delta_m^0$, the current strength N_n and current stiffness K_n will be constantly used in the softening area. In this model, N_0 can be taken as the real interface strength. Therefore, it is crucial to define N_{\min} . In general, it needs several elements in the softening cohesive zone R to obtain stable numerical simulations of the interface crack propagation. In this study, for instance, for Mode-I case, from the following definition of softening area [2],

$$N_c R_n = \frac{\pi E_{polymer}}{2} \frac{G_{IC}}{N_{\min}^2} \quad (3)$$

where N_c is the number of elements in softening area, which can be set to be 2~5 from our numerical experiences, R_n is the element size and $E_{polymer}$ is the Young's modulus of polymer. $N_c R_n$ is the size of softening area. Finally, N_{\min} depending on the element size can be defined as follows,

$$N_{\min} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi E_{polymer}}{2} \frac{G_{IC}}{N_c R_n}} \quad (4)$$

Finally, this cohesive model is implemented at ply interfaces combined with a 3D brick hybrid finite element for plies [4] in the explicit time integration scheme.

Figure 1: Schematic view of adaptive cohesive model ($\alpha=0\sim 1.0$).

3 VERIFICATIONS

3.1 A DCB problem

A DCB problem [1] shown in Fig. 3 is analyzed using the traditional and adaptive cohesive models, respectively. The properties of cohesive element are given in Table 1. The mesh size and predicted N_{\min} are listed in Table 2 when $E_{polymer}=3.0$ GPa and $N_c=3$. The comparison with the experimental results [1] is shown in Fig. 4. The results of traditional cohesive model have sudden stops due to very strong numerical instability. Also, the results of our previous technique called as move-limit [3] for stabilizing the numerical computations are plotted. From Fig. 4, we can find that this technique can yield stable numerical results. Also, the proposed adaptive model can yield stable results. Furthermore, the errors in the peak load given by the adaptive cohesive model are much smaller than those of move-limit technique [3], especially when the mesh size is large.

3.2 A low-velocity impact problem

As shown in Fig. 5, a quasi-isotropic CFRP plate of 32 plies as $[(45^0/0^0/-45^0/90^0)_4]_s$ is impacted by an impactor with the mass of 4.6kg and impact energy is 6.0 J. The properties of lamina are: $E_1=135.0$ GPa, $E_2=E_3=10.0$ GPa, $G_{12}=G_{13}=5.50$ GPa, $G_{23}=4.50$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.0183$, $\nu_{13}=0.45$, $\nu_{23}=0.25$, $\rho=1489$

Figure 2: Constitutive law of adaptive cohesive model.

Figure 3: A DCB problem

Table 1. Properties of cohesive element

N_0 (MPa)	K_0 (N/mm ³)	G_{IC} (kJ/m ²)	δ_m^0 (mm)	δ_m^f (mm)
45	3.0×10^4	0.378	0.0015	0.0119

Table 2. Predicted N_{min} in Eq. (4)

Mesh size R_n (mm)	Initial $N_0 \rightarrow N_{min}$ (MPa)
1.0	45.0 \rightarrow 22.5
2.0	45.0 \rightarrow 15.0

Figure 4: Results of DCB problem.

kg/m³. Also, the properties for delaminations are: $N_0=85.0$ MPa, $S_0=T_0=106.0$ MPa, $N_{min}=76.5$ MPa, $S_{min}=T_{min}=95.4$ MPa, $G_{IC}=0.5$ kJ/m², $G_{IIC}=G_{IIIC}=1.0$ kJ/m². The modified Hertz contact law [5] is employed to deal with the contact between the impactor and the plate. To reduce the computational cost, since the maximum size of delaminations is small from experiments, only in the central area of 35mm×35mm, along the thickness direction, 32 brick elements at 32 plies are placed plus 30 cohesive elements at 30 interfaces between plies (at the midplane, there is no cohesive element). The mesh size in this area is 2.5mm×2.5mm in plate plane.

Figure 6 shows that numerical and experimental impact force histories. The numerical result agrees with two experimental results very well. Figure 7 shows the delaminations obtained by computation and ultrasonic scan at the impacted side along the thickness direction. Again, very good numerical result was obtained.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we proposed a new cohesive model for simulating the delamination propagation when using comparatively coarse meshes. Two examples have shown the effectiveness of this model. Due to comparatively large mesh used, this method can be employed for simulating the delamination damage

of large composite structures.

Figure 5: CFRP specimen of 32 plies.

Figure 6: Comparison of impact force history.

Figure 7: Comparison of delaminations

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